

Polarographic Study of Some 6-(aryl)-imidazo [2, 1-b] thiazole-3-acetic acids and 6-(aryl)-imidazo [2, 1-b] thiazole-3-acetates

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Manuscript received 19 November 1979, revised 15 April 1980, accepted 12 June 1980

The polarographic behaviour of some derivatives of imidazo [2,1-b]-thiazole-3-acetic acid and imidazo [2,1-b]-thiazole-3-acetate has been studied over a range of pH values and concentration. No reduction waves have been found but catalytic hydrogen evolution waves were observed and compared with those obtained for thiamine in phosphate buffer.

It has been reported¹ that imidazo-thiazole nucleus possesses anti-inflammatory activity, so some derivatives of this nucleus were prepared by Sawhney and coworkers² and tested for their anti-inflammatory activity. A survey of literature reveals that the chemistry of imidazo thiazoles has developed quite large as the chemistry of other heterocycles, but application of polarography towards the study of these compounds is very limited and only one case³ has been noted.

The present paper summarizes the results of polarographic study of some derivatives of 6-(aryl)-imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole-3-acetic acids I(a)-I(c) and its acetates II(a)-II(e).

6-(p-X-phenyl) imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole-3-acetic acid.
I(a) X=H I(b) X=Br I(c) X=NO₂

6-(p-X-phenyl)-imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole-3-acetate.
II(a) X=H II(b) X=Cl II(c) X=Br
II(d) X=OCH₃ II(e) X=NO₂

Experimental

Apparatus : An LP-7 polarograph with automatic pen recorder EZ-7 was used. The sensitivity of the polarograph was 10 μ A full scale. The temperature of the solutions was kept constant at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The pH of the solutions was measured with Photovolt digital pH meter. Saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode.

Reagents and solutions : Acetate buffers in the pH range 3.5-5.5 were prepared. Since the solubility of all the imidazo thiazole derivatives in water was

very small, $1 \times 10^{-5}M$ solutions of all the compounds were prepared in absolute alcohol. The potassium chloride used as supporting electrolyte was of 'AnalaR' grade. The solution of potassium chloride, sodium acetate and acetic acid was prepared in triple-distilled water.

The solutions of the compounds were kept at a low temperature to prevent hydrolysis.

Procedure : Test solutions were prepared by taking 6.00 ml of the acetate buffer, 1.00 ml or so of absolute alcohol and 1.00 ml or as the need was, of imidazo thiazole solution. The quantity of absolute alcohol was varied to retain the same concentration (20% V/V) of alcohol in all the test solutions. The ionic strength was kept constant by adding 2.00 ml of 1.75M potassium chloride. Before recording the polarogram, the test solution was deaerated by passing purified nitrogen gas for about 15 minutes.

The study was carried out at three different pH values namely 4.2, 4.6 and 4.92.

Results and Discussion

The imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole derivatives studied are absorbed at the surface of the DME as indicated by the lowering of the droptime curve (Fig. 1). This surface character is probably due to the large molecular weight of these compounds.

Effect of pH : The waves observed are very sensitive to pH changes and are well defined only in the pH range 4-5. The wave height decreases with increasing pH⁴. Although the wave height increases below pH 4, the formation of plateau diminishes and this makes the measurement of wave height more difficult. This can easily be understood from the fact that the catalytic waves are due to reduction of hydrogen. Lowering the pH, increases the concentration of hydrogen ions and hence the wave height. This is in agreement with the behaviour of catalytic waves⁶ which show strong dependence upon pH.

Fig. 1. Drop time curve of substance (Ia), (1) The supporting electrolyte, (2) $1.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ (Ia) in the supporting electrolyte, (3) $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ (Ia) in the supporting electrolyte.

Fig. 2. Polarograms of (IIb) at pH (4.2). Mercury column height: (1) 30; (2) 40, (3) 50 and (4) 60 cm. Curves starting at $-1.15 V$.

Effect of mercury pressure height : As the height of mercury column is increased, the wave height decreases. The decrease in wave height is small due to the presence of alcohol and this confirms the catalytic character of the waves^{6,7} (Fig. 2).

Effect of concentration of the depolarizer : The catalytic waves found are measurable at $4 \times 10^{-6} M$ for imidazo [,1-b] thiazole-3-acetates and at 2×10^{-5} for imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole-3-acetic acids.

The half wave potential of the compound II(a) was found to be a linear function of the concentration of II(a) (Table 1) which is in agreement with the theory of catalytic waves^{5,6}. Also, there exists a linear relationship between wave height and

TABLE 1

Concentration/M	E 1/2 V/S. S.C.E.
6.00×10^{-5}	-1.9380V
8.00×10^{-5}	-1.9500V
1.10×10^{-4}	-1.9710V
1.50×10^{-4}	-1.9960V

concentration of the compound when the concentration range is 0.004-0.06 mM for imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole-3-acetates and 0.04-0.11 mM for imidazo [2,1-b] thiazole 3-acetic acid derivatives. The nitro derivatives show the normal reduction waves at a low negative potential.

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